
IMPACT OF EXCHANGE RATE AND FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study conducted an empirical investigation on the impacts of exchange rate and FDI on agricultural productivity in Nigeria, from 1986-to 2018. The study made use of the vector autoregressive (VAR) method for analysis. Test for unit root was conducted using the augmented dickey fuller statistic, while Johansen statistic was used to test for the long-run relationship among the datasets. The data were stationary and had a long-run relationship. Results from the study found that FDI and foreign exchange rate impact negatively on agricultural output in Nigeria. With this, the study concluded that an increase in the exchange rate is detrimental to agricultural output in Nigeria, while FDI increases have inhibited the productivity of the agricultural sector in the country. The study recommends that the economy of Nigeria should be re-diversified to improve the value of the Naira and ensure that the inflow of foreign direct investments aids productivity in the agricultural sector.

Keywords: FDI, Agricultural Productivity in Nigeria, Exchange rate

1. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of agriculture in economic growth could be summed into four categories, which are food provision, the supply of raw materials to the manufacturing sector, contributing to employment opportunities and serving as a source of foreign earnings (Enoma, 2010). Agriculture plays the following roles in economic development: product contribution, factor contribution, market contribution, foreign exchange contribution, employer contribution and contribution to the welfare of the rural people (Todaro & Smith, 2015). Consequently, the agricultural sector is critical to achieving global poverty reduction targets. According to IDA (2009), agriculture is the single most important productive sector in most low-income countries, often in terms of its share of Gross Domestic Product and almost always in terms of the number of people it employs. More so World Bank (2008) asserts that agriculture is a vital development tool for achieving the Millennium Development Goal that calls for halving by 2015 the share of people suffering from extreme poverty and hunger. Hence the sector could be rightly said to be a sine qua non in an economy.

The agricultural sector has been the driver of the Nigerian economy a decade after independence (Oriakhi, 2003). The sector absorbed 70% of the workforce of the country and

guaranteed a viable economy that was largely self-reliant in the area of food production. More so, the sector contributed to about 60% of the total national output between 1960 and 1969; contributing to about 70% of foreign earnings as well. Albeit, joining the membership of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) in 1971 led to the neglect of the sector by the Nigerian government. Specifically, the decline in agricultural output level and its contribution to the growth of the Nigerian economy does not mean that the sector has been displaced by the attractive oil sector, but has recorded low output due to neglect by the government as the oil sector became the major foreign exchange earner of the economy (Michael, 2017).

The sector witnessed a persistent decline in output, dropping in national output to an average of 33.6% and 33.4% in 1970 and 1979, and 1980 and 1989 respectively. Invariably the Nigerian economy imported agricultural outputs that it could naturally produce. This created structural imbalances, whereby sub-sector of the Nigerian economy (such as the manufacturing sector) which depended on agricultural growth, grossly underperformed. Okojie (2003) stated that with the emergence of the oil glut in the 1970s witnessed economic challenges as the Nigerian economy became bankrupt. The Nigerian economy was able to overcome the financial challenges of the 1970s; however, the economy became an indebted economy borrowing from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) through the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP). However, the lesson had been learnt on the relevance of the agricultural sector to economic growth in Nigeria as the diversification of the economy witnessed an economy dominated by the non-oil sector, particularly led by the agricultural sector. To this effect, the IMF report (2014) revealed that the Nigerian economy grows at about 6.8 per cent mainly owing to a continuing strong performance in the non-oil sector (primarily agriculture, services, and trade).

There are factors responsible for explaining productivity in Nigeria's agricultural sector. Two factors are of primary concern to this study. One of the factors is the availability of capital. The government has been the major supplier of funds and capital to the agricultural sector in the country since its independence in 1960 (Iyoha, 2003). Capital is critical to the growth of agriculture in Nigeria and beyond, and its poor provision contributed to the poor performance of the sector in the country between the 1970s and 1980s when the government redirected capital and funds to the oil sector. The Nigerian economy was deregulated in 1986, thereby limiting government interference in economic activities in the country; thereby warranting that the agricultural sector should be driven by the private sector. The private sector, on the other hand, is poorly developed, as it is mostly dominated by small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) that have little capital to successfully drive the agricultural sector in the country (Osemeke, 2011). Invariably, bank loans are not a reliable source of acquiring capital in Nigeria, considering the nature of interest charges and poor bank to agriculture lending framework in the country (CBN, 2003). The need for capital to drive the agricultural sector in Nigeria then makes it imperative to consider capital from foreign direct investments (hereafter, FDI). This is embedded in the huge advantages accruing from foreign direct investments. FDI poses a lesser risk compared to bank loans as a source of agricultural financing because it does not require repayment (Danmola, Olateju & Aminu, 2017). Also, FDI comes with the transfer of factors that complement capital, such as managerial skills, organizational structure and skills, and technological inflow (Falki, 2009; Umehukwu & Okezie, 2018).

Also, the exchange rate plays an important role in agricultural sector performance in Nigeria. This is because the sector requires mechanized tools for large scale output, rather than crude implements that can only provide for subsistent needs (Lawal, Nwanji, Asaleyeye & Ahmed, 2018). Depreciation of the Naira would make the importation of this agricultural equipment to be cost, which would both raise the cost of production and likely reduce output level

(Olubukoye, Adedoyin, Eneogu & Olorunkanmi, 2018). In some cases, an extreme high exchange rate would bring about jettison plans to engage in agricultural activities because of expensive foreign capital input. The situation becomes more worrisome knowing that the exchange rate in the country has steadily increased as the Naira has consistently depreciated against the US Dollars, since the foreign exchange rate market was deregulated in September 1986. From ₦1.75 to USD1 in 1985, the foreign exchange rate was at ₦306.9 for USD1 in 2019; which has increased by almost 300%. Recently, the foreign exchange rate in Nigeria is around ₦380 for USD1. The deteriorating nature of the Naira against the US Dollars thus makes it difficult to import capital for agricultural purposes in Nigeria.

The need to focus on FDI and exchange rate as determinants of agricultural sector performance in Nigeria arises from their unfavourable trends in recent times. The country enjoyed an increase in FDI from ₦0.7 billion in 1986 to more than ₦1.3 trillion in 2011. However, an inflow of these funds declined to ₦875.1 billion in 2013 during the time the Boko-haram terror started to reign in the country, and further declined to ₦602.1 billion in 2015. It later increased in 2016 and 2017 when it was above ₦1 trillion, but further lowered to ₦610.4 billion at the end of 2018. A disturbing statistic was provided by Oloyede (2014), which revealed that an increase in FDI in Nigeria has seen a large percentage of the fund going to the oil sector and the banking sector, with little funds allocated to the agricultural sector. This then questions the role of the Nigerian government in encouraging a greater inflow of funds to the agricultural sector. As already revealed, the exchange rate is constantly increasing, as the Naira deteriorates rapidly in the foreign exchange market. These statistics do not mean well for the agricultural sector in Nigeria. It thus becomes important for this study to enlighten the Nigerian government and all stakeholders on plausible dangers facing the agricultural sector, in the midst of poorly performing foreign direct investment and foreign exchange rate.

Already, literature is proliferated with empirical studies on FDI and agricultural sector performance (Oloyede, 2014; Yusuff, Afolayan & Adamu, 2015; Akinwale, Adekunle, Obagunwa & Busayo, 2018; Agba, Adewara, Nwanji, Yusuf, Adzer & Abbah, 2018), as well as exchange rate and agricultural sector performance (Oyakhilomen, Falola & Kekwot, 2014; Adekunle & Ndukwe, 2018; Olubukoye, Adedoyin, Eneogu & Olorunkanmi, 2018). Yet there is a scarcity of studies that investigated both FDI and exchange rate. Many of these studies did not provide robust results to offer richer empirical insights. It, therefore, becomes imperative to readdress these issues, by engaging both FDI and exchange rate as determinants of agricultural productivity in Nigeria and using the Granger causality method to offer robust empirical results.

Research Objectives

The broad objective of this study is to determine the impact of exchange rate and FDI on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. This comprises specific objectives, which are to:

1. Analyse the impact of exchange rate on agricultural productivity in Nigeria.
2. Investigate if FDI exerts an impact on agricultural productivity in Nigeria.
3. Ascertain exchange rate granger causes agricultural productivity in Nigeria.
4. Determine whether FDI granger causes agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

To achieve these objectives, this paper is divided into five sections. Section one already covered the introduction and problem statement while section two contains a detailed review of both theoretical and empirical literature. Section three deals with model specification, while section four is concerned with data analysis, interpretation and discussion of results and finally section five contains the conclusion and recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature

The role of capital injection on agricultural sector productivity has been emphasized in the literature. This was properly demonstrated in Arthur Lewis's "theory of dual sector" in 1954 (Jhingan, 2012). The theory explained how the injection of labour and capital would help to achieve the development of an agricultural sector. It was suited for developing countries, which operated a dual-sector economy, where the informal and formal sectors operated along with each other (Todaro & Smith, 2015). For developing countries, a subsistent, informal agricultural sector operated along with the large-scale, formal agricultural sector. Lewis recognized that there is the availability of excess labour in the informal agricultural sector which has inadequate capital that incapacitates productivity; while the formal agricultural sector has adequate capital, but lacked sufficient labour input (Jhingan, 2012). Lewis then demonstrated that the transfer of surplus labour from the informal sector to the formal sector, would improve labours' welfare through increased earnings, and also bring about an increase in agricultural productivity. Lewis's theory is drawn from the Physiocrats theory of agriculture. While the latter established the notion that agriculture produced a net product that can spur economic growth, the former provided a systematic explanation of how the net product can be achieved via labour supply and capital injection. Lewis' theory recognizes that as capital accumulates with increased production, economic growth becomes achieved (Puri & Musa, 2016).

The availability of capital for agricultural growth and expansion has remained a challenge faced by many developing countries, such as Nigeria. It is in this regard that Chenery and Strout (1966) formulated the two-gap theory based on the Harrod-Domar model, to explain how economies can achieve growth and development via the injection of foreign capital (Hunt, 2007). Foreign capital inflow could be achieved via foreign loans, foreign debt, portfolio investment, or foreign direct investment (FDI) (Muhammad, Nor & Sallahuddin, 2016). However, FDI enjoys greater benefits than foreign debt and foreign loans, because it does not require repayment (Danmola, Olateju & Aminu, 2017); and it promises higher returns via the transmission of managerial skills, organizational structure and skills, and technological inflow (Falki, 2009; Umechukwu & Okezie, 2018). Also, foreign direct investment enjoys greater benefits than portfolio investment because it conveys a lasting interest in the economy (Odusola, 2003). FDI has greater interest among foreign investors, compared to portfolio investment. It thus offers developing countries greater opportunities to acquire capital, managerial skills, organizational structure and skills, and technological inflow for improved agricultural productivity.

Lewis' theory of dual sector economy and the two-gap theory by Chenery and Strout (1966) does not recognize the contributions of exchange rate on agricultural performance, yet the literature offers relevant insights. The purchasing power parity (PPP) theory serves as a theoretical framework to understand the negative effects of foreign exchange rates on agricultural productivity, via inflationary trends. The PPP theory was developed by neoclassical economics to show the relationship between exchange rate and purchasing power between two countries. It originated with the School of Salamanca during the 16th Century but was developed in its modern form by Gustav Cassel in 1920 (Akinniran, 2016). The theory posits that the exchange rate between two nations is equal to the ratio of the currencies' respective purchasing power. Therefore, two currencies are in equilibrium or at par when

a basket of goods (taking into account the exchange rate) is priced the same in both countries. The relative version of PPP is calculated as:

$$S = \frac{P_1}{P_2} \quad (1)$$

Where S is the exchange rate of currency 1 to 2, P_1 is the cost of goods x in country 1, and P_2 is the cost of goods x in country 2. Conversely, Abiodun et al (2016) restated equation (1) as:

$$P_t^a = S * P_t^* \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) implies that domestic price at time t is determined by world import price and the nominal exchange rate. Therefore, variations in S, P_t^* or both of them will affect P_t . However, because of trade frictions, the law of one price may or may not hold in certain instances. This is based on the fact that many factors such as cost of production, producers' mark up and exchange rate movements influence domestic import prices (Abiodun et al, 2016). Based on the purchasing power parity theory, the link between the foreign exchange rate and agricultural sector productivity can be clearly understood. For developing countries that depend on the importation of mechanized tools for agricultural productivity, the exchange rate plays an important role in the level of productivity in the sector (Lawal, Nwanji, Asaleye & Ahmed, 2018). An increase in the foreign exchange rate would raise the cost of capital, and through inflation, may have a negative impact on agricultural productivity. Conversely, a decrease in the foreign exchange rate would lower the cost of capital, which in turn would lower inflationary pressure and may encourage agricultural productivity (Olubukoye, Adedoyin, Eneogu & Olorunkanmi, 2018).

Empirical Literature

Several empirical studies have explained the relationship between FDI, exchange rate and agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Oloyede (2014) carried out an empirical study on the impact of FDI on agricultural development (proxied using agricultural output) in Nigeria, using time series data from 1981 to 2012. The empirical analysis was based on the OLS technique. Findings showed that FDI has a positive impact on agricultural development in Nigeria. This result is consistent with Akinwale, Adekunle, Obagunwa and Busayo (2018), whose vector error correction methodology (VECM) analysis found a positive impact of FDI on agricultural output in Nigeria between 1986 and 2015. Slight differently, Agba, Adewara, Nwanji, Yusuf, Adzer and Abbah (2018) made use of the error correction methodology (ECM) and found that FDI only had a significant positive impact on agricultural output in Nigeria, between 1981 and 2014. Yusuf, Afolayan and Adamu (2015) also made use of the vector error correction methodology (VECM) and found no significant relationship between FDI and agricultural output in Nigeria, between the periods 1977 and 2010.

In other literature, Olubukoye, Adedoyin, Eneogu and Olorunkanmi (2018) engaged the vector error correction methodology (VECM) and found a negative significant relationship between exchange rate and agricultural sector output in Nigeria between 1986 and 2016. Oyakhilomen, Falola and Kekwot (2014) investigated the impact of exchange rate on agricultural sector output using the vector error correction methodology (VECM) method and found that exchange has a negative significant impact on agricultural output in Nigeria between 1986 and 2011. Adekunle and Ndukwe (2018) also investigated the relationship between exchange rate and agricultural sector output in Nigeria, between periods of 1981 and 2016 with the aid of the non-linear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) method. The study provides no evidence of test for linearity between the exchange rate and agricultural sector output in Nigeria. Results obtained showed that exchange rate exerted a significant impact on agricultural output in Nigeria, but differently. The increasing effect of exchange rate had both positive and negative

significant impacts on productivity in the sector, as time varied; while the decreasing effect of exchange rate also had both positive and negative significant impacts on productivity in the sector, as time varied. One period lag increasing and decreasing effect of exchange rate exerted a significant negative impact on agricultural output; while increasing and decreasing effect of exchange rate exerted a significant positive impact on agricultural output.

Based on these results, the vector error correction methodology (VECM) method is mostly used in the empirical literature on the subject matter; however, it is important to understand the relationship between FDI, exchange rate and agricultural productivity in Nigeria may not be linear, as hinted by Adekunle and Ndukwe (2018), whose study needs to be improved upon because it does not provide evidence of test for linearity between exchange rate and agricultural sector output in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

The first and second research objectives will be analysed using regression analysis. Albeit, the regression model for this study draws from an adjusted two-gap model by Chenery and Strout (1966). The model originally recommends that developing countries should attract the inflow of foreign capital to foster productivity. Several studies (Hunt, 2017; Muhammad, Nor & Sallahuddin, 2016; Danmola, Olateju & Aminu, 2017; Umechukwu & Okezie, 2018) recognize that FDI can aid domestic productivity in developing countries, where there is often a deficit of capital for production. However, in recent times, the exchange rate has been recognized as an important factor that determines agricultural productivity among developing countries, because they depend on the importation of capital for mechanized agriculture (Lawal, Nwanji, Asaleye & Ahmed, 2018; Olubukoye, Adedoyin, Eneogu & Olorunkanmi, 2018). An increase in the foreign exchange rate affects agricultural output through inflation; and vice versa. Therefore, an amended two-gap model recognizes the impact of FDI and exchange rate on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. In this regard, a regression model will be specified to capture the impact of FDI and exchange rate on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. The model draws from the models of Oloyede (2014); and Olubukoye, Adedoyin, Eneogu and Olorunkanmi (2018), which recognize the impact of exchange rate and FDI on agricultural output in Nigeria. This is mathematically stated as:

$$AGY = f(EXR, FDI) \quad (1)$$

Where: AGY = Agricultural Output

EXR = Exchange rate

FDI = Foreign Direct Investment

Equation (1) is adjusted to suit this study. Interest rate, inflation, and population are included as control variables. Therefore, equation (1) is restated as:

$$AGY = f(EXR, FDI, INT, INF, POP) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) is expressed in econometric form as:

$$AGY = \alpha + \beta_1 EXR + \beta_2 FDI + \beta_3 INT + \beta_4 INF + \beta_5 POP + U \quad (3)$$

Where: AGY = Agricultural productivity (measured using real agricultural output)

EXR = Exchange Rate (measured using nominal exchange rate)

FDI = Foreign Direct Investment

INT = Interest rate (proxied using monetary policy rate)

INF = Inflation rate (proxied using consumer price index)

POP = Population

α = Total Factor Productivity

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Parameter Estimates

U = Stochastic Disturbance Error Term

Equation 3 will be estimated using the Vector-Autoregressive (VAR) technique to mitigate the problem of endogeneity. A unit root will be conducted using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) statistic, while the long-run relationship will be examined using the Johansen co-integration statistic.

To analyse the third and fourth research objectives, this study will engage the VAR Granger causality method. This is to ascertain whether the exchange rate and FDI can be used to forecast values of agricultural productivity in Nigeria. The granger causality models for this study are stated as:

$$AGY = \delta_0 + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_1 AGY_{t-j} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_2 EXR_{t-j} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_3 FDI_{t-j} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_4 INT_{t-j} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_5 INF_{t-j} + \sum_{p=1}^k \delta_6 POP_{t-j} + V \quad (4)$$

Where: δ_0 is the intercept; δ_1 to δ_6 are parameter estimates; V is the error term; t-j are lag lengths; while 'k and p' are periods.

4. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Statistics	AGR	FDI	EXR	INT	POP
Mean	8.488483	394.4849	101.8484	13.77273	133.0932
Median	7.817084	225.2000	118.5667	13.50000	128.5961
Maximum	17.54415	1360.300	306.0837	26.00000	195.8747
Minimum	2.891672	0.700000	1.754523	6.000000	85.76640
Std. Dev.	5.081429	411.5497	85.97696	3.895291	33.01314
Skewness	0.434847	0.756250	0.662245	0.705133	0.326158
Kurtosis	1.654218	2.295541	2.903119	4.748653	1.919600
Jarque-Bera	3.530308	3.827886	2.425031	6.939126	2.190071
Probability	0.171160	0.147498	0.297448	0.031131	0.334528

Source: Author's Compilation (2020)

In table 1, FDI averaged ₦394 billion between 1986 and 2018, which has a high standard deviation of 411.55 to suggest that the inflow of funds from foreign direct investors is considerably low during the years. Agricultural productivity averaged ₦8.48 trillion, which deviates by 5.08. This indicates that the agricultural sector performed well during the years 1986 to 2018. Exchange rate averaged ₦101.85 for USD 1 between these years, with a low standard deviation value (85.97696) that indicates high depreciation of the Naira over these years. The interest rate has an average value of 13.7%, which also has a low standard deviation (3.9%). This shows that the rate of borrowing money was mostly double-digit between 1986 and 2018. The population, on the other hand, averaged 13309 million. The standard deviation (33.01314) is low and thus reveals that the country experienced high and stable population figures during the years. Kurtosis values are lower than 3.0, except for interest rate. This implies that many of the datasets have an absence of outliers in their distributions. Jarque-Bera probability values show that only the interest rate is not normally distributed. Both Kurtosis

and Jarque-Bera probability values provide evidence that it is appropriate to adopt parametric statistics to analyse the data for this study.

Figure 1: Trend Analysis

The figure shows the graphical representation of the growth pattern of Agricultural Productivity (AGY) in Nigeria in response to Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and Exchange Rate (EXR).

Stationarity Test Analysis

Table 2: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test Results

Variables	95% Critical values	ADF Test Stat	Order of Integration
AGY	-3.562882	-5.217181	I(1)
FDI	-3.574244	-5.293275	I(1)
EXR	-3.562882	-4.187737	I(1)
INT	-3.562882	-7.738380	I(1)
INF	-3.612199	-6.424244	I(1)
LAB	-3.644963	-6.206269	I(1)

Source: Author’s Compilation (August 2020)

Table 2 presents the ADF test results for the presence of stationarity in the datasets. The results show that the datasets are all stationary at first difference.

Co-integration Analysis

Table 3: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace) Results

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.806786	144.7243	95.75366	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.669210	93.76157	69.81889	0.0002
At most 2 *	0.627182	59.46711	47.85613	0.0028
At most 3	0.409354	28.88053	29.79707	0.0635
At most 4	0.294017	12.55781	15.49471	0.1321
At most 5	0.055336	1.764707	3.841466	0.1840

Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

*Denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author’s Compilation (August 2020)

Table 4: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue) Results

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.806786	50.96269	40.07757	0.0021
At most 1 *	0.669210	34.29446	33.87687	0.0446
At most 2 *	0.627182	30.58658	27.58434	0.0200
At most 3	0.409354	16.32271	21.13162	0.2066
At most 4	0.294017	10.79310	14.26460	0.1649
At most 5	0.055336	1.764707	3.841466	0.1840

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

*Denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author's Compilation (August 2020)

Tables 3 and 4 show the Johansen test results, using the trace and max-eigen statistics. In both tables, there are three cointegrating equations. This implies that there is a long-run relationship between agricultural output, FDI, exchange rate, inflation rate, interest rate, and population.

VAR/VECM Regression Results

Table 5: Regression Results

VAR Variables	Coefficients	VECM Variables	Coefficients
Intercept	-5.07767	Intercept	-18.0306
AGY(-1)	0.5480*	D(AGY(-1))	0.1847
AGY(-2)	-0.1436	D(AGY(-2))	0.0717
FDI(-1)	-0.0004	D(FDI(-1))	-0.0007*
FDI(-2)	-0.0007	D(FDI(-2))	-0.0012*
EXR(-1)	-0.0055	D(EXR(-1))	-0.0287*
EXR(-2)	0.0164*	D(EXR(-2))	-0.0304*
INT(-1)	0.0390	D(INT(-1))	0.0625*
INT(-2)	-0.0240	D(INT(-2))	0.0166
INF(-1)	0.0005	D(INF(-1))	-0.0003
INF(-2)	0.0009	D(INF(-2))	-0.0011*
POP(-1)	7.4146*	D(POP(-1))	-10.3320*
POP(-2)	-7.5340*	D(POP(-2))	16.2913*
		ECM	-0.9678*
R-squared	0.9962	R-squared	0.8436
Adjusted R-squared	0.9936	Adjusted R-squared	0.7165
Serial correlation Test	0.0926	Serial correlation Test	0.0681

Source: Author's Compilation (August 2020)

Table 5 shows the VAR and VECM regression results. In the VAR results, the long-run impacts of FDI, exchange rate, interest rate, inflation rate, and population on agricultural productivity are presented; whereas the VECM results show the short-run impacts of FDI, exchange rate, interest rate, inflation rate, and population on agricultural productivity. From these estimates, FDI had a negative impact on agricultural productivity in Nigeria, both in the short and long-run periods. The impacts are only statistically significant during the short-run period. Similarly, exchange rate exerted negative significant impacts on agricultural productivity during the short-run period; but exerted a positive significant impact on productivity from the sector during the long-run period. On the other hand, the interest rate had a positive significant impact

on agricultural productivity in Nigeria only during the short-run period. Inflation also exerted a significant impact on agricultural productivity in Nigeria during the short-run period. The population had a significant impact on agricultural productivity in Nigeria, both in the long run and short-run periods. The impacts varied in both periods. One period lag value of population reduced agricultural productivity in Nigeria, but contributed positively to output from the sector in the long run; while another hand, the two-period lag value of population exerted a positive impact on agricultural output during the short run and lowered output from the sector during the long-run period.

Based on these results, FDI inflow is harmful to agricultural sector productivity in Nigeria, but during the short-run period. Long-run impacts are also negative, but not statistically significant. Also, exchange rate contributes negatively to productivity in agriculture in Nigeria, during the short run, whereas it promotes performance in the sector in the long run. Interest rates and inflation rates are detrimental to agricultural productivity in Nigeria, only in the short run. Long-run impacts are not statistically significant. Lastly, the population is observed to exert diverse impacts on productivity from agriculture in Nigeria; some of which are positive and also negative. The regression estimates are non-spurious to explain the determinants of agricultural productivity in Nigeria. This is because the adjusted r-squared values are high, indicating that the exogenous variables (FDI, exchange rate, interest rate, inflation rate, and population) strongly explained variations in agricultural performance in Nigeria between 1986 and 2018.

Granger Causality Analysis

Table 6: VEC Granger Causality Result

Dependent variable: D(AGY)			
Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
D(FDI)	15.40878	2	0.0005
D(EXR)	44.63689	2	0.0000
D(INT)	15.27654	2	0.0005
D(INF)	0.138199	2	0.9332
D(POP)	68.15548	2	0.0000
All	79.59969	10	0.0000

Source: Author's Compilation (August 2020)

Results from table 6 show that except for the inflation rate, the rest of the exogenous variable granger caused agricultural sector productivity in Nigeria. As such, FDI, exchange rate, interest rate, and population can be used to forecast values of agricultural output in Nigeria.

5. CONCLUSION

This study shows that FDI has not contributed to the growth and development of the agricultural sector in Nigeria. Instead, the inflow in foreign direct investments has contributed to the decline in productivity in the sector. While this result does not agree with several empirical studies (Yusuff, Afolayan & Adamu, 2015; Akinwale, Adekunle, Obagunwa & Busayo, 2018; Agba, Adewara, Nwanji, Yusuf, Adzer & Abbah, 2018), Oloyede (2014) remarked that inflow in FDI in Nigeria has been biased against the agricultural sector, rather, favouring the oil and bank sectors. It then becomes understandable that an increase in FDI in Nigeria contributes negatively to agricultural productivity because it contributes to the withdrawal of labour from the agrarian sector to other sectors that attract FDIs. On the other hand, there is evidence that an increase in the foreign exchange rate is harmful to agricultural productivity in Nigeria. This agrees with many studies (Oyakhilomen, Falola & Kekwot, 2014;

Olubukoye, Adedoyin, Eneogu & Olorunkanmi, 2018) that found a negative relationship between agriculture and foreign exchange rate in Nigeria. With these situations, it is pertinent to address FDI and foreign exchange rate situations in Nigeria, if their negative impacts on the agricultural sector would be reversed. First, there is a need to re-diversify the Nigerian economy to improve the value of the Naira; such that rediversification of the economy would attract foreign direct investors to the agricultural sector.

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